

On the Vacuum State of Relativistic Quantum Field Theories

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A Lorentz invariant vacuum theory for quantum field theories is proposed based on causal symmetric representation of relativistic quantum fields.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A vacuum state of a relativistic quantum system is the base state from which the Fock space for the quantum system can be generated based upon the quantum fields describing the system. A proper understanding and representation of it under Lorentz transformation is one of the key steps towards building theories on how classical physical spacetime (of Einstein) could emerge from quantum field theoretical one, which will be referred to as *a priori* spacetime (of Kant) in the subsequent articles on the topic. The requirement that the said vacuum state, like the speed of causal front (namely, speed of light in the true vacuum), is an invariant entity under Lorentz transformation constitutes a sufficient condition for such a program to be consistently established..

However, vacuum states of widely adopted relativistic quantum field theories can not be rendered invariant under Lorentz transformation due to the non-local nature of quantum packets, which is represented by the well-known Heisenberg uncertainty relationship

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (1)$$

The reason for it will be explained in more details in the sequel. It implies a kind of Aether of quantum nature, the effects of which is not observed, is hidden somewhere, causing inconsistencies when physical covariance under Lorentz transformations of Special Relativity is required. Some of these inconsistencies are studied in [4] using quantum field theoretical method popular in particle physics. It is expected to appear also in studies of quantum gravity where there will be no room for such inconsistencies to be removed because all kind of energy-momentum source causes gravity, especially troubling ones are those infinite ones, under currently widely adopted approaches and understanding of General Relativity.

The present article provides a more generic view and propose a consistent representation under which the underlying relativistic quantum system should transform during a Lorentz transformation so that the one vacuum requirement can be met, paving the way for an attempt at the task mentioned at the beginning.

II. MICROSCOPIC CAUSALITY

Quantum Mechanics (QM) is characterized by, amongst others, the non-commutativity of its conjugate operators, like between position \hat{q} and momentum \hat{p}

$$[\hat{q}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar, \quad (2)$$

and many others. When ordering of operators that can be associated with physical measurements makes a difference, the process of ordering must be consistently and coherently organized using the concept of time¹ to establish the notion of “before” and “after”.

Time interval is absolute or global in Newtonian spacetime with its sign independent of what reference frame an observer is in. However, it is relative in Relativity because it’s local in nature. One of the manifestation of the said nature is that for two events separated by a space-like distance, it is possible that their time difference changes sign when an observer changes his/her reference frame. Since the wave function of a particle, upon which operators in Eq. 2 operates, can not be localized in both of its conjugate variables, for it is distributed on a space-like hyper-surface for any given time in a chosen reference frame, the said observer will discover a different QM (see Eq. 2) when the sign changing boundary is crossed after performing a reference frame adjustment which results in witnessing a flipping of sign for the right hand side of Eq. 2. Therefore any space-like hyper surface acts like a discontinuous cut (in time or conjugate energy variable) which implies that physics at the most fundamental level depends on how the cut is approached if the time reversal operation is not represented properly.

Albeit a reader may argue that the sign on the right hand side of Eq. 2 is a matter of convention, but that is only true in Newtonian spacetime. The fact that relativistic QM theoretical framework contains physical operations/dynamics within itself that can mix different conventions, that is the fundamental problem. It implies that, an *a priori* extension of QM developed in Newtonian spacetime to Relativistic spacetime should lead to a categorically different one at the fundamental level.

However it can be shown that the conventional low energy QM is still a valid approximation in the Standard Model (see [4]) because only electromagnetic force dominates there. It is both fortunate because it does not delay the rapid

¹ The scale or metric for time does not matter here, only the sign is of significance.

development of QED that is shown to be consistent with observed phenomena and unfortunate because it delayed the discovery of the inconsistencies uncovered here.

An extension to conventional quantum field representation is proposed in [4] based on a two dimensional representation of causal time reversal (CTR) (see also [2]) transformation. Albeit the said reference deals with spin 1/2 particles, it can be generalized in the following

$$\Phi \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

for any other kind of particles, where $\phi_{1,2}$ are both conventional quantum fields living on corresponding opposite edges of the ‘‘cut’’ mentioned above, to realize a consistent representation of Lorentz covariance. Here, ϕ_1 is a causal field and ϕ_2 is its retro-causal companion. They are related to each other by a spacetime mirror reflection $\widehat{\mathcal{M}}$ operation:

$$\Phi(x) \xrightarrow{\widehat{\mathcal{M}}} \Phi_{\mathcal{M}}(x) = \mathcal{M}O_1\overline{\Phi}^T(-x) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{M}\overline{\phi_2}^T(-x) \\ \mathcal{M}\overline{\phi_1}^T(-x) \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

with superscript ‘‘T’’ denoting operator transpose,

$$O_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

the first of the three Pauli matrices, and \mathcal{M} an operator² that operates on the internal degrees of freedom of $\phi_{1,2}$, through the so called reality condition:

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{M}}(x) = \Phi(x). \quad (6)$$

It represents the requirement that physics on both side of a discontinuous space-like hyper surface (see the above discussion) are *CPT* images of each other. For spin 1/2 particles (see Ref. [4]),

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{M}}(x) = \gamma^5\Phi_{\mathcal{CPT}}(x). \quad (7)$$

Detailed representation of the mirror operation and reality condition is/will be provided in other studies, It’s sufficient to stay at current level of abstraction for the purpose of the current study.

I shall not delve further into the rabbit hole of the meaning of retro-causality in the current article. This is discussed in quite details in the philosophical oriented literature. Suffice it to say that contemporary discussions in literature are mostly based on the so called motion-reversal representation of time reversal (see [2] and [4]) and most of the ideas that are required to maintain Lorentz covariance are built into the current relativistic quantum field theories. These attempts are not complete because of the cross space-like hyper surface discontinuity problems that Ref. [4] and the current article are trying to resolve. The one considered here is called causal reversal representation of time reversal that does make a physical difference as it is shown in the sequel. In addition, retro-causality is in the *a priori* spacetime, causality the emergent physical spacetime that is empirically accessible will be a different one, since it’s a trace over (with proper weight) the contributions of the 1 and 2 components (see Sec. IV).

III. LORENTZ TRANSFORMATION

Suppose that there are two reference frames \mathcal{S}_A and \mathcal{S}_B whose coordinate systems are chosen to align in the same direction. \mathcal{S}_B is moving at speed v in the direction of the common x axis. Then a spacetime point $[t, x, y, z]$ for \mathcal{S}_A and the corresponding one $[t', x', y', z']$ for \mathcal{S}_B are related to each other by a Lorentz transformation:

$$ct' = \gamma(ct - vx) = ct \cosh \vartheta - x \sinh \vartheta \quad (8)$$

$$x' = \gamma(x - vt) = x \cosh \vartheta - ct \sinh \vartheta \quad (9)$$

$$y' = y \quad (10)$$

$$z' = z \quad (11)$$

² Note this is different from the one used in Ref. [4], here the O_1 is extracted out.

where

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}, \quad \cosh \vartheta = \gamma, \quad \sinh \vartheta = \gamma \frac{v}{c}. \quad (12)$$

and c the speed of causal front (or speed of light in true vacuum). There are two ways to perform the transformation of Eqs. 8 to 11 for an observer

Case A: The observer changes his/her reference frame from \mathcal{S}_A to \mathcal{S}_B . And does observations on his/her canonical hyper surface at $t' = 0$.

Case B: The observer stays in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A and perform the mathematical transformation only. And does observations on a space-like hyper surface defined by $t' = 0$ instead.

The first case is the default assumption in studies of Special Relativity. The second one is also often used in studies of an observer in accelerated reference frame (e.g. in accelerated \mathcal{S}_B) and General Relativity. It is listed here since it's relevant to the discussions below and it provides a hint on how and what kind of gravity could emerge from a relativistic quantum system described by the causal symmetric theory proposed in the current article. Lorentz covariance (or equivalence principle) requires that physics on the $t' = 0$ canonical hyper surface in reference frame \mathcal{S}_B to be the same as the space-like hyper surface defined by $t' = 0$ in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A .

This is however not a trivial task for a quantum system. The mathematical covariance of QFT under Lorentz transformation of **Case A** is already studied in the literature, they are, however, physically valid when the assumption that the vacuum state in different Lorentz frames are all the same (or equivalent) is made.

A. Fock space and space-like hyper surfaces

It is a natural assumption that the Fock space \mathcal{F} is independent of the reference frames and coordinate systems that an observer takes. The vacuum state $|0\rangle$ is the *ab initio* state of \mathcal{F} in which there is no particle, namely for any annihilation operator \hat{a} in any field, like ϕ , that the quantum kinematics of the system is described

$$\hat{a} |0\rangle = 0. \quad (13)$$

It should be emphasized that the *ab initio* vacuum state defined here is a mathematical ideal that is different from the ground state of an interacting system. It's the ground state only when all interactions are turned off.

1. The conventional approach

In the conventional approach, assuming that the state $|0\rangle$ on the $t = 0$ hyper surface in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A is the true vacuum state, namely Eq. 13 is satisfied. Since only utterly trivial and non-physical field configuration, if possible at all, can render a field ϕ to be identical on both of the hyper surfaces $t = 0$ and $t' = 0$ in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A under arbitrary spacetime map of Eqs. 8 to 11, an annihilation operator \hat{a}' in ϕ on hyper surface $t' = 0$, which evolves in the t' direction, in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A becomes a linear combination of annihilation \hat{a} and creation \hat{a}^+ operators defined on the $t = 0$ hyper surface in the same reference frame. Therefore when the observer switches to reference frame \mathcal{S}_B , a Lorentz boost can be performed on the internal degrees of freedom of ϕ so that the form of equations for ϕ remains invariant and it's various parts covariant, For spin 1/2 particle, the boost transformation is

$$\phi' = U\phi \quad (14)$$

$$U = e^{-\frac{i}{2}\vartheta K^{01}} \quad (15)$$

$$K^{01} = \frac{i}{4} [\gamma^0, \gamma^1] \quad (16)$$

which is well known (see, e.g. [1]). Despite the apparent covariance in form, the state on the $t' = 0$ hyper surface will be found to be not the vacuum state that satisfies

$$\hat{a}' |0\rangle = 0 \quad (17)$$

with a' arbitrary annihilation operator inside of any field of the system, in reference frame \mathcal{S}_B . So vacuum state can not be consistently continued from one reference frame to another in an Lorentz invariant manner that satisfies

Eq. 13. It implies that the Fock spaces defined by Eq. 13 are associated with the specific reference frame chosen, there is no means to connect them quantum mechanically where unitarity could be kept.

This is one of the origins of many inconsistencies related to Lorentz covariance found (e.g. in [4] section III.D and the following sub-section).

2. *The non-relativistic nature of the Dirac Sea and how it is removed*

The fields $\phi_{1,2}$ above are operators. They alone do not provide a full description of the physics behind the QFT represented by them. One must provide a proper interpretation of their particle content so that Lorentz invariance is maintained.

Dirac introduced his Sea, in which all negative energy states are already filled, to prevent a relativistic fermion to continuously falling into the negative energy states, represent by the negative solutions of the equation under his name, based upon Pauli's exclusion principle. Feynman formalized it in the formulation of relativistic QFT by adding an additional rule which allows particles (or solutions of relativistic single particle equation) with positive energies to propagate forward in time only and those with negative energies to only propagate backward in time, which is reinterpreted as anti-particles that should also propagate in the forward time direction³. Such a rule applies not only to fermions, but also to bosons as well. It is equivalent to a choice of complex continuation scheme of the energy variable p^0 for a particle into its complex plane in Mathematics. More specifically, Feynman's rule stated above is equivalent to letting p^0 to stay below the real axis when its real part is negative and stay above the real axis when its real part is positive to get around poles on the real axis for p^0 . Making a choice amongst several possible p^0 contours on its complex plane is mathematically necessary for consistency. Feynman's choice renders the perturbation theory for the QFT to be seemingly invariant under Lorentz transformation, but it is not sufficient, which could be revealed when one inspect it more closely because of the hidden assumption (or restriction) mentioned above, namely all particles and their corresponding anti-particles have to propagate **forward in time** only. It is inherited from the causality requirement in classical physics where all particles are localized. However, quantum packets are non-local on the space-like hyper surface, which is represented by the fact that their propagator between two spacetime points are extended beyond the time-like causal region, for their coordinate difference, on one side of the corresponding light cone into the space-like one on the other side. However the sign of a time interval between two space-like spacetime points can have opposite signs in two reference frames in relativity, which is discussed in section II. This is not representable in the contemporary formulation of relativistic QFT. It leads to inconsistencies, which manifest in the existence of extra divergencies in perturbation theories that can be traced to the existence of the Dirac Sea, in which only half of Fock space states are filled, forming a Fermi surface that is a non-scalar under Lorentz transformation. An example of them is the so called "chiral anomaly" that violates \mathcal{CP} and \mathcal{T} invariance found in gauge theories that respect the said symmetries if one follows conventional formulation of QFTs, which is discussed in relatively details in a subsequent work [5].

The Dirac Sea is an Aether like entity that is not an invariant one under a Lorentz transformation. The Dirac Sea in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A , in which all negative energy states are filled, is mapped into a non-Dirac Sea like entity in which some of the negative energy states, which are filled, are mapped into positive energy states and some of the positive energy states, which are empty, are mapped into negative energy states in reference frame \mathcal{S}_B when a Lorentz transform that relates the two reference frames is performed on the states in the Dirac Sea involved.

It can be seen that all the above mentioned problems and inconsistencies have a common root cause, namely classical causality which can not be maintained in a true relativistic invariant formulation of QFT due to the non-local nature of quantum packets in QM, Retro-causal physical processes must be taken into account and represented properly.

The solution of the current theory is to use a two dimensional, causal symmetric representation given by Eq. 3 together with the reality condition Eq. 6 to solve the problem. Here the Dirac Sea for ϕ_1 is mapped into an inverted Dirac Sea for ϕ_2 in which all positive states are filled according to Eq. 6. The corresponding "Dirac Sea" of the current theory is thus equivalent to a state in the Fock space in which all states are either all empty or all filled. It was shown in the section II.E.1 of Ref. [4] that there are two types of representation of the \mathcal{CPT} transformations, which should not be mixed if \mathcal{CPT} symmetry is to be respected⁴, in which the so called "type-I" representation corresponds to the kind of "Dirac Sea" where all states are empty and the "type-II" one corresponds to a different "Dirac Sea" where all states are filled. Such a map results from the fact that it can be shown the former type always leads to finite vacuum expectation value for the corresponding current and the later one always leads to infinite results. The all empty one and the all filled one are all scalars, or they remain the same in difference Lorentz frames. Therefore, the physical one

³ An anti-particle is represented by the lack of corresponding negative energy state or a hole in the Dirac Sea.

⁴ Unlike the contemporary relativistic QFT, the \mathcal{CPT} symmetry is not a formal mathematical theorem here, but a choice that are physically most natural one.

corresponding to the ‘‘type-I’’ representation of \mathcal{CPT} , namely the $|0\rangle$ of the current theory, is literally a relativistic vacuum state.

3. Vacuum invariance

Vacuum invariance follows from the reality condition Eq. 6. Let’s write down the following identity:

$$\Phi(x) - \Phi_{\mathcal{M}}(x) = \Phi(x') - \Phi_{\mathcal{M}}(x') = 0 \quad (18)$$

which is true under the constraint of Eq. 6. It is independent of what reference frame an observer chooses. It follows that

$$\Phi(x') = \Phi(x) + \mathcal{M}O_1 [\bar{\Phi}^T(-x') - \bar{\Phi}^T(-x)], \quad (19)$$

where x' is related to x via the Lorentz transformation Eqs. 8 to 11. It means that for particles in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A , its field operator $\Phi(x)$ that evolves on the hyper surface $t = 0$ has a one to one mapping to $\Phi(x')$ that evolves on the hyper surface $t' = 0$, if the transformation 19 is performed. It also means that the vacuum state $|0\rangle$ defined on hyper surface $t = 0$ that contains no particle remains empty on $t' = 0$ hyper surface in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A . Therefore an observer can switch to reference frame \mathcal{S}_B and use the same vacuum state $|0\rangle$ without having to redefine the Fock space to keep his/her notion of vacuum state valid and identifiable with the one in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A .

Since Eq. 19 is valid between any equal time hyper surfaces that is related with each other via the Lorentz coordinate transformation of Eqs. 8 to 11 in same reference frame \mathcal{S}_A , it is better to be written in differential form, consider an infinitesimal Lorentz boost $\delta\vartheta$ in the direction defined by a unit vector \mathbf{n}

$$\delta\Phi(x) = \mathcal{M}O_1 \mathbf{n} \cdot (\mathbf{x}\partial_0 + ct\nabla) \bar{\Phi}^T(-x) \delta\vartheta, \quad (20)$$

here \mathbf{x} is the 3-vector $[x, y, z]$ and $\partial_0 = \frac{1}{c}\partial_t$.

B. Covariant time derivative in a coordinate system representing acceleration

Consider time evolution of ϕ in an accelerated coordinate system

$$\frac{\delta\Phi(x)}{\delta ct} = \partial_0\Phi(x) + \frac{1}{c^2}\mathcal{M}O_1 \mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{x}\partial_0 + ct\nabla) \bar{\Phi}^T(-x) \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{a} is the 3-acceleration vector. It can also be written in a more familiar form

$$\frac{\delta\Phi(x)}{\delta ct} = \partial_0\Phi(x) - \frac{1}{c^2}\mathbf{a} \cdot (\mathbf{x}\partial_0 + ct\nabla) \Phi(x) \quad (22)$$

which $\bar{\Phi}^T(-x)$ is replaced by $\Phi(x)$ according to the reality condition with the same condition applied to the final solution.

C. Principle of equivalence and a possible mechanism for gravity

Equivalence principle requires that an observer in reference frame \mathcal{S}_B , which is accelerating relative to reference frame \mathcal{S}_A with an acceleration \mathbf{a} , of a particle that is accelerating with the same acceleration \mathbf{a} due to gravity in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A sees no gravitational effects.

Eq. 21 tell us that if gravity is dynamically generated from within the system itself, then it is possible to maintain equivalence if the emergent gravity could effectively cancel out the second term, which involves a rotation in its upper and lower components, in the emergent spacetime (see bellow). That is, Eq. 22 that includes gravity should be

$$\frac{\delta\Phi(x)}{\delta ct} = \partial_0\Phi(x) - \frac{1}{c^2}\mathbf{a} \cdot [\mathbf{x}\partial_0 + ct\nabla - \mathbf{\Gamma}_{grav}^0(x)] \Phi(x) \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{\Gamma}_{grav}^0$ is induced by gravity.

It can be seen that the equivalence principle is harder, if possible at all, to maintain if the spacetime manifold is already curved by gravity at the quantum level, since again particle wave function supported by $\Phi(x)$ is not localized

on a space-like hyper surface. Suppose reference frame \mathcal{S}_B is a free falling one. According to standard differential geometry, there is only one spacetime point p' in reference frame \mathcal{S}_B , which is identical to the tangent Minkowski space, for any given spacetime point p in reference \mathcal{S}_A . However the wave functions of particles represented by Φ extends beyond the corresponding points in both reference frames, a consistent non-local mapping rule from reference frame \mathcal{S}_B to \mathcal{S}_A for field Φ at points around the p' and p with unlimited extension is required⁵. Otherwise, the equivalence principle can not be upheld. Whether or not the machinery of differential geometry can be of help here remains an interesting question to be explored.

As it is shown in [4], the meta-stable superfluid phase of strong interaction system does mix the upper and lower components of the quark fields. It would be interesting to investigate its quantum effects further. A detailed account of the exploration of this possibility is presented in another article.

IV. EMERGENT SPACETIME

Given a set of Fock space \mathcal{F} mixed states which are defined by a QFT $\mathcal{S} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{|s\rangle | s \in \mathcal{F}\}$ that constitutes a particular classically localizable⁶ physical entity of interest, the measured value of the spacetime coordinate of $[\hat{c}t, \hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z}]$ operators for the said entity in a pre-selected reference frame \mathcal{S}_A which are their expectation values

$$\hat{c}t = \int d^3x \bar{\Phi}(\mathbf{x}, t) c t \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (24)$$

$$[\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z}] = \int d^3x \bar{\Phi}(\mathbf{x}, t) [x, y, z] \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (25)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the 3-space coordinate on the hyper surface at constant t on which the 3-integration is performed, is generated by an average over the set of expectation values

$$[\bar{c}t, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}] = \sum_{\mathcal{S}} w(s) \langle s | [\hat{c}t, \hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z}] | s \rangle \quad (26)$$

where the $w(s)$ is weight (or eigenvalue of a known density matrix) of the state $|s\rangle$ in an assemble and the summation is over all members of the set \mathcal{S} is defined on a hyper surface with fixed time. It is not guaranteed that $[\bar{c}t, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}]$ transform the same as Eqs. 8 to 11 under Lorentz transformations in conventional approaches.

It is expected that the 4-dimensional space containing $[\bar{c}t, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}]$ is not a flat one in general since there is no guarantee that the metric for them is always the Minkowski one. However, since various space-like hyper surfaces are constructed to be equivalent in the present formulation, infinitesimal small differences in $[\bar{c}t, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}]$ does transforms according to Lorentz transformation from reference frame \mathcal{S}_A to \mathcal{S}_B despite the fact that they may not be a flat spacetime manifold anymore. Thus the mapping is conformal.

V. SUMMARY

The possibility of constructing a covariant framework for relativistic quantum fields on space-like hyper surfaces is presented based on the basic premise that the *ab initio* vacuum state, or the absolute nothingness, is an invariant entity in different coordinates and reference frames. A direct consequence of it is that it also implies the invariance of the corresponding Fock space build on top of it.

It also removes some conceptual uncertainties regarding the particular selection of the $t = 0$ hyper surface to define physical observables in an earlier work [3].

⁵ This is already a problem to resolve at the classical level. For example the Maxwell equations predict that an accelerating charged particle emits electromagnetic waves, which are non-particle like (or non-localized) entities, in a proper inertial reference frame. The prediction is verified by empirical facts. Let's assign it to reference frame \mathcal{S}_A . But does an accelerating observer in a reference frame, say \mathcal{S}_B , sees the existence of non-vanishing electromagnetic radiations from the same charged particle in reference frame \mathcal{S}_A that stays motionless just by joining reference frame \mathcal{S}_B ? Apparently not since this violates energy conservation because it implies that physical radiations could come out of the subjective intension of an observer! But it would if Maxwell's equations has the same form in reference frame \mathcal{S}_B .

⁶ Photons, which are massless, are not localizable in the classical limit of $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ or $n_\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, where n_γ is the number of photons in a random or thermal ensemble. It converges to or emerges as extended classical EM waves governed by Maxwell equations.

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